

FAMILY LAW REFORMS IN RELATION TO MUSLIM WOMEN IN INDIA: A COMPREHENSIVE DEBATE ON ENTRY POINTS AND THEMATIC AREAS

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Family Law Reforms in Relation to Muslim Women in India: A Comprehensive Debate on Entry Points and Thematic Areas

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Religious and socio-cultural policies can be rightly categorised as “wicked” problems, with no optimal solution in sight. Some even go to the extent to claim that in a pluralistic society, it is almost impossible to earmark a definite public good, because it would have different meanings for different people. Even the most optimal of solutions would have qualifications riding on it (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

The “wicked problem” tag holds true for policy debates on Muslim Personal Law (MPL) in relation to Muslim women in India. The paper has been subdivided into three entry points and six conceptual thematic areas to the debate. The three entry points are: “Multiculturalists versus Feminists”; “Law, Religion and Patriarchy”; and “Secularism and its Concerns”. The six thematic conceptual areas are: “Consolidation of Identity through Colonial Rule”; “Overriding of Customs and Consolidation of Identity”; “Secularism and National Unity Discourse”; “Test on the Anvil of the Constitution”; “Political Expediency”; and “Administrative Convenience and Codification”. It has been done to get a comprehensive coverage of the policy areas that can affect (positively or negatively) the issue at hand.

The paper would initially attempt to throw light on the normative-theoretical political elements (global and national) of the debate. The abstract part would be covered by the entry points “Multiculturalists versus Feminists” and “Law, Religion and Patriarchy”. Since both these entry points are abstract in nature, a link to the context would also be established in order to bring out its relation to the policy in question. The entry point “Secularism and its Concerns” would address the public policy concerns with secularism in India. The entry points take a bird’s-eye view. They are more concerned with a broader debate, of which MPL is just one of the sub-areas.

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The thematic areas take a more contextual approach to policy debates regarding MPL. The thematic areas of “Consolidation of Identity through Colonial Rule” and “Overriding of Customs and Consolidation of Identity” are more concerned with developments influencing the MPL in the pre-independence era. “Secularism and National Unity Discourse” is focussed on the discourse affecting MPL during the time of independence. “Test on the Anvil of the Constitution” touches upon the Constitutional position of personal laws and more specifically, MPL. To round up the discussion, the paper ends with the thematic area of “Administrative Convenience and Codification”.

The reason for selecting these entry points and thematic areas is to signify the various intersecting ideas that have come to affect the debate on Muslim family law reforms in India. The question to which the paper wants to direct attention is whether these debates have contributed to ameliorating the condition of Muslim women? Or have they only allowed to deflect the attention to multiple peripheral issues that the cause of Muslim women has been lost in the process? The paper would also try to direct attention to some normative and theoretical ideas that should be brought to the mainstream (in turn, pushing the digressing ones to the backburner) if the debate has to be steered in the right direction.

Three Entry Points

The three entry points are those that have been usually the go-to areas to make an entry into the MPL debate. The utility of these entry points in relation to the MPL debate would be the subject of discussion.

Multiculturalism versus Feminism

The first entry point to the debate on MPL can be the primarily theoretical and abstract debate between political theorists, often called the multiculturalism versus feminism debate. Multiculturalism works with the assumption—sometimes in principle, and most of the times in practice—that the norms within the cultural community might not be consistent with the principles of the liberal democratic order. The cultural practices might violate the basic norms of liberty and equality that are highly valued in a democratic setup. According to feminists, these violations are usually inflicted on the weakest section in the group, the burden of carrying multiculturalism falling on them (Pollitt, 1999). Feminists are of the opinion that no matter if it is the majority or the minority culture, the burden of oppressive culture practices is carried by women (Okin, 1999). The degree of oppression might vary from culture to culture.

The turf of oppressive religious and socio-cultural practices lays the ground for an extensive theoretical debate between multiculturalists and feminists. It is necessary to lay emphasis on the debate because it is very similar to the one witnessed in India. India fulfils the criteria under the realm of which the discussion is taking place. India is a liberal democratic country espousing secular credentials, with each religion having personal laws that are disadvantageous to women within the community. It is no surprise that many theorists use India as a case study in their debates. An attempt would be made here to further find similarities and dissimilarities, as well as the debate's usefulness in the Indian experience.

It is not to be assumed that multiculturalists have totally ignored the weaker sections in any cultural group. Will Kymlicka (1995, p.7) has even come up with a formula to prevent the oppression of weaker sections within minority communities. He makes it clear that while the cultural minority group is entitled to external protections, it does not mean it can impose internal restrictions on the members of the community. The recognition of internal restriction depicts that multiculturalist scholars have been aware of the problems weaker sections within minorities face. It can also be contended that the Indian Constitution already has the above features mentioned by Will Kymlicka. The Indian Constitution provides freedom of religion (external protection) but subject to public order, health and morality (bar on internal restrictions). The exercise of freedom of religion is further subject to the other provisions of Fundamental Rights.

Nonetheless, the efforts made by multiculturalists for the interests of women have been seen highly lacking by feminists in ameliorating the situation of women within minority cultures. Okin (1999) is highly critical of the advocates of group rights. She accuses multiculturalists of looking at groups as a monolith and says that they completely ignore the private sphere. She points to the gendered nature of all cultural groups. Okin is critical of the highly gendered nature of "personal laws". Okin opines that it is due to the propensity of men to dominate women in the culture, that personal laws are usually attributed to be a critical part of any culture. Okin's views are pathbreaking because she cites the domination of women by men in the private sphere as the principal reason for paying obeisance to their culture. It is from Okin's critique that a few ideas have emerged within the theoretical debate to solve the problem of oppression of women through personal laws.

First, an emphasis is laid on the ability of the liberal democratic state to provide a robust option for an exit for any person not subscribing to the collective good of the culture (Wienstock, 2004). An option of exit may also coerce the group to act justly towards its members, though serious doubts have been raised on the idea of exit as it does not take into account the inability of

the internal minority of women to gain economic freedom, or skills to survive (Schachar 2001, p.41). It also discounts the psychological burden of exit and might pressurise women to exit rather than improving the conditions within culture (Reitman, 2004).

It would be interesting to note that there is no option for exit of an individual before marriage from religious personal laws in India. The suggestion of exit misses the point that an exit might have other externalities. Exit option is not restricted to the realm of personal laws that include marriage, divorce, adoption, and inheritance, but also, they extend to other areas of public life such as freedom of worship or running a religious institution. If one wants to escape any particular religious personal law, they can convert to another religion. An option of exit is available in India in the form of Special Marriage Act, 1954. All the reasons given above for apprehension from exit are quite logical in the Indian case. Only an alternate proposal given by a feminist group from Delhi, Working Group Women's Rights has proposed "reverse optionality". It would give women the option to shift from secular laws to personal laws if they felt that the personal laws are more beneficial to them, but the secular laws would initially be there for all (Anveshi Law Committee, 1997).

Second, an interesting discussion that has taken place in the theoretical realm is how to read the situation when women who are not ready to give up religious and cultural practices which are usually considered oppressive or discriminatory. What if women consider the culture and practises too essential for their faith and follow it on their own volition? Okin's (1999) solution to it is rather simplistic: She wants any discussion on minority cultural rights to involve younger women in the group and see if certain practices are crucial to "being a woman" in the culture. Okin mistrusts the average older women in patriarchal culture to fight for change because they have already adapted, have a psychological need to force it upon the younger generation, already occupy a relatively higher and powerful position in the society, and can use it upon the women lower in the hierarchy such as the daughters-in-law.

To expand on the liberal approach, Marilyn Friedman (2003, p.179-204) suggests an autonomy-based approach that leans towards liberalism for accepting or rejecting culture-based practices with respect to women. Rather than giving importance to democratic approach, she prioritises a variant of liberalism. According to Friedman, the true consent of women would come about in three conditions: ability to choose among an array of alternatives; without any coercion, manipulation or deception; and ability to develop the capacity to make decisions for themselves. Such a content-neutral autonomous approach has promise, but lacks a mechanism for implementation.

Monique Deveaux's (2004) deliberative democracy approach takes a more practicable form when it comes to reconciling multiculturalist and feminist positions. She uses the example of South Africa to arrive at a model of deliberative procedure to bring reforms in the oppressive cultural practices against women. She agrees that the model will not lead to a wholesome transformation, but would propose revisability of current norms. Non-domination and political equality are the important features of this model, but how to remove the unelected leaders acting as spokespersons of the religious minority from the decision-making process remains a question. If the exclusion of religious leaders as middlemen is not possible, two inclusions in the deliberative process can be thought about that can dilute the role of the unelected middle one. One of them could be leaders elected from the democratic process, and the other can be the civil society organisations fighting for the rights of women in the community. It is because the legitimacy of the spokespersons of the community rests on the cultural practices being followed.

Third, Okin's views are also challenged for assuming values of liberalism as evidently self-true (Parekh, 1999). An-Na'im (1999) warns not to establish liberal individualism as the norm and extinguish other cultures in the guise of it. Bhabha (1999) is of the opinion that the moral high ground liberalism takes leaves women to choose between benevolent western liberal patriarchy and indigenous patriarchal culture. Martha Nussbaum (1999) views political liberalism as a better option over comprehensive liberalism as it provides enough liberty for freedom of religion.

The interesting feature of this discussion is the familiarity with the Indian condition. If we replace Western majoritarian notion with the Hindu majoritarian notion, a similar process is playing out. MPL is being attributed as being highly gendered by opponents of it who take a moral high ground and call for it to be repealed in favour of a Uniform Civil Code (UCC) (Kishwar, 1994). The political leaders who call for non-interference are banished on the charge of favouring conservatives and reactionaries, and against reform in MPL. Then there is a section who favours internal reforms within the culture itself. Hence, we see all the above theoretical discussion playing out in India itself.

Law, Religion and Patriarchy

The second entry point of law, religion and patriarchy begins with pointing out that law is Janus-faced (Dhavan, 2001). It has the difficult task of satisfying the powerful, and at the same time, justifying the ideals it is working for, thus gaining legitimacy in the process. This aspect of law is all the more applicable in the aspect of reform in gendered personal laws. Archana

Parashar (1992, p.23-45) goes much more into depth to clarify the significance and limitations of legal equality. She firstly clarifies that legal equality is a much narrower goal than the goal of gender equality. Secondly, even legal equality, according to her, is a far off goal in the case of India. She has argued that many opportunities to bring to affect comprehensive equality have been foiled by legislators because they found it in violation of Indian culture. Thirdly, if and when the goal of legal equality is achieved, there are low chances that the changes would reflect on the ground.

Scholars across the umbrella ideology of feminism have questioned the notion of “impartiality of law” itself. Feminists have emphasised that it is the social, political and economic factors that influence the process of law making (Parashar, 1992, p.23-45; Agnes, 2011, p.xxi-xxxi). It is highly likely that law reforms do not affect structural changes. It is because of the institutionalisation of the gendered differences that are visible in the legal realm, too. Feminists by the means of “perspective scholarship” aim to break the inherent gendered notions of the society (Agnes, 2011, p.xxi-xxxi).

Many feminists work with the assumption that the state is an agent of patriarchy. Freeman (cited in Parashar 1992, p. 28) asks if the state is just a reflection of the social institution of patriarchy and reinforces the male dominance, can it be expected to serve women in working for reforms in law and towards a non-patriarchal society? Indian feminists (Parashar, 1992, p.23-45; Agnes 2011, p.xxi-xxxi; Hasan 2018) working on the subject of religious personal laws, recognise the dual and contradictory role of the state in bringing social reforms for women. In some cases, the state views religion as a hurdle to be removed, and in other cases, a patriarchal ally. Zoya Hasan (2018) takes the view that the former role is played by the state as a modernist that transforms traditional loyalties into modern ones. The latter role allows the state to reaffirm narrow cultural values borrowed from the past. Naturally, communal conflicts and accompanying insecurity would aid in reinforcing patriarchal practices. For the state, it becomes the easiest form of appeasement. Also, it helps take away attention from the little amount of work done by the state in improving the condition of the beleaguered minority, the Muslims in this case. Srimati Basu (2005) feels the need to demystify the state. In other words, identifying the disparate elements and interests that make up the state. It would help to analyse the workings in the realm of personal laws.

The discussion leaves the question of what makes the fight over legal equality important for Indian feminists. Parashar (1992, p.33) believes that irrespective of whether the changes in law bring any actual changes, they have a symbolic meaning. Agnes (2011, p. xxiv) agrees and says that Indian society is struggling with a “justice crisis” in terms of personal laws. It is something that needs to be resolved and cannot be left alone merely because it may not bring about any change on ground.

Secularism and its Concerns

The third entry point of secularism in India has a wide canvas. Not everything falling under the realm of Indian secularism can be covered in this paper, but a few relevant points can be touched upon. While Rajeev Bhargava has played a huge role in separating Indian secularism from Western secularism, scholars like TN Madan (2009), Ashish Nandy (2006), Achin Vinayak (cited in Chandhoke, 2019) and Akeel Bilgrami (cited in Chandhoke 2019) have debated over the appropriateness of current model of secularism for India. Undoubtedly, secularism does have a role to play when it comes to discussion on MPL. A few relevant policy debates related to these normative-theoretical debates would be discussed in the paper.

A theoretical principle more relevant to public policy that has been given both by Bhargava (2011) and Madan (2006) on Indian secularism is the “minority-majority syndrome” or “majority-minority conundrum” respectively. The principle helps to place the crisis of Indian secularism in the right perspective. Bhargava (2011) reveals that there is a need to recognise the irreducible difference between diverse cultural backgrounds. If it is not recognised, the communitarian egalitarianism can turn into communalism. Madan (2006) agrees that recognising the anxieties and sensitivities of the minority is essential. The syndrome in Indian secularism arises from the lack of disconnection between law and policy which otherwise is considered the rock bed of Western secularism. The state is constantly questioned for how much interference in both majority and minority religion is acceptable.

Madan raises the pertinent question of where we ought to draw the line? He also points to the “selective secularism” by leaders of the minority where they do not want the same thing by themselves, that they expect from the Hindu Right. He points out that after the Partition of the Indian Subcontinent, Muslim fundamentalist organisation Jamaat-i-Islami (Hind) did accept a secular government, but only due to utilitarian expediency and not in principle. Government actions in the face of political expediency gave further rise to the idea of the minority enjoying a status of privilege. The actions of both the Government, as well as the leaders of the minority, allowed the Hindu right to highlight the protected status enjoyed by Indian Muslims. The Hindu Right marked Muslims as a community which was not ready to change, and had the backing of the Government. It is natural that in the topic of our study, the reform in MPL, contestations over secularism would form a big part of the debate.

There is a sense of despondency amid the political theorists of secularism, despite the extent of writings on the subject. The theories and ideas have hit a cul-de-sac (Rajan & Needham, 2006). Amid the sombre mood on the subject, Chandhoke (2019) has pressed on the importance of the need to look beyond

secularism and focus on the ideas of substantive equality for minorities. She also asks the intellectuals to not let go of the subject easily because they are the bulwark of secularism and gender justice in the country.

Six Thematic Areas

The study can now focus on the thematic categories that are directly related to MPL in order to completely focus on the study at hand. A logical flow has been maintained in choosing the thematic areas keeping a chronological order in mind.

Consolidation of Identity through Colonial Rule

It has been well established in social sciences that making and consolidation of identity is a process of solidifying imagined communities. The identity of an Indian Muslim has also passed through different phases, in order to come to the point, it is today. Satish Saberwal (2006) explores if the identity of Indian Muslims was always as homogenous as it is today, or if there was social fragmentation within the group. When it comes to the mediaeval period, Saberwal points to the slow spread of Islam and low enthusiasm to create a distinct Islamic identity. There might have been a push by some sections of ulema that Muslims live by the shariat, but due to the rulers being rarely theocratic, the process proceeded slowly. Saberwal points to the startling revelation that social complexity was prevalent in mediaeval India among Muslims much more than the Hindus. There was a sharp division between the immigrant and the so-called high class ashraf Muslims, and indigenous converts from lower caste and artisan class called *ajlaf* Muslims.

The recruitment of Indians in the Muslim fold needs to be focussed on learning more about how conversions took place during the mediaeval period in the rule of Delhi Sultanate and the Mughals. Saberwal (2006) places the conversions on a continuum that ranges from peaceful to coercive conversions in order to take into account the concern of forced conversion that is often focussed on by the Hindu Right. He lays emphasis on the limited presence of coercion and the lack of emphasis on following a strict code by those who had converted to Islam.

With the loss of the Muslim rule with the advent of the British, internal and external processes resulting in the homogenisation of the Muslim identity gained pace. At first, it was the external process of the British that began the churning towards what came to be understood as the “religious” personal laws. Warren Hastings had started with the policy of cultural federalism, so that each community may be subject to their own personal laws (Rudolph & Rudolph, 2001). The British were of the opinion that since the British legislature cannot make the Mohammedan and Hindu religion, they cannot make their laws either (Dhagamwar 1989, p.54). But still, the process of

making of the Hindu and Mohammedan “personal laws” has often been attributed to the colonial regime in India.

First, the British relied on pandits and maulvis to inform them about the rules of the religious laws. This arrangement was abandoned as early as 1864 with customs being given a higher degree of recognition. But the scriptural understanding had gained some ground by then (Parashar 1992, p.68). It is what Agnes (2011) terms as Anglo-Hindu or Anglo-Mohammedan laws. Second, the scriptural or the customary interpretation had to abide by the British understanding of “justice, equity and good conscience” (Agnes 2011, p.8). Once a decision was taken by the judicial stream, it resulted in establishing a precedent for future cases. It is what Agnes terms as Anglo-Saxon jurisprudence. Finally, there was a creation of “personal law” that could be specifically called colonial (Chhachhi 1994; Parashar 1992; Agnes 2011), eventually leading to “religious laws” and “personal laws” being used interchangeably. Amrita Chhachhi (1994, p.82) is quick to point out that it was the colonial regime that “established a particular family structure—patriarchal, patrilineal and monogamous—as the norm. The post-colonial state inherited and maintained these institutional structures of separate personal laws to regulate the family”.

The 1857 uprising put a halt to the colonial project of evangelical and utilitarian inspired liberal universalism in India. Queen Victoria’s proclamation of 1858 moderated the project of rationalisation and universalisation (Rudolph & Rudolph, 2001). The doctrine of non-intervention by the British still did not give up the goal of social reform, though obviously it was less explicit than before. It paved the ground for the discussion of internal factors within the Muslim community that led to the complete supersession of customs and in turn the homogenisation of the identity of the Indian Muslim.

Overriding of Customs and Consolidation of Identity

The uprising of 1857 also affected how the yet-fragmented Muslim community started to see itself. The Muslims were targeted by the British, as they saw them playing an influential role in the uprising. The difficulty of the situation and the social anxieties that had been developing led to a response that would go on to establish the umma, an Islamic community (Saberwal, 2006). The dual focus on sharia, the Islamic law, along with the urge to lead a purer way of life as a means to create a homogenous identity was visible after the 1857 uprising.

First, the thoughts of eighteenth-century Islamic scholar Waliullah were influential, who felt that the community of Islam in India could be consolidated following the pious way of life prescribed by sharia (Madan,

2009, p.136). Secondly, new institutions and means of communication were available to allow for social restructuring. According to Metcalf (1982), it was the madarsa of Deoband, established in 1867, that took the lead role in restructuring and inspiring other institutions to follow. The ulema by then had a strong hold in society and Deobandis also trained men to be knowledgeable in sharia. An emphasis was put on how to differentiate and distance from the Hindus by process of de-casting, abandoning folk deities, etc. The practices that can be deemed as Hindu or in violation of the sharia were to be systematically rooted out in order to create a separate identity of Indian Muslims. Third, what aided in cementing the identity was the collective experience of violence and conflict between Hindus and Muslims (Saberwal 2006).

Later in Indian colonial history, three important players emerged within the Muslim community who have been identified as the key stakeholders on the subject of MPL. The first one is the All-India Muslim League founded in 1906. They were modernist in thought and represented the economic and political interest of the Muslim elite. The second one was the Jamiat-ul-Ulama-i-Hind (Jamiat, established in 1919) that aligned with the Indian National Congress (INC) and supported the Khilafat movement in 1920. The Muslim League were too progressive for their liking as they were striving for a modern and secular state. They were more comfortable with the INC as it stood for pluralist coexistence (Hasan 1988). Their whole programme revolved around a single issue of sharia. They emphasised that the custody to understand and interpret sharia lies with the ulema. Madan (2009) categorises them as moderate fundamentalists. The third one was Jamaat-i-Islami (Jamaat, established in 1941) led by Abdul ala Maududi that was a critique of both of the above organisations. It adopted the position of even implementing sharia in the aspect of criminal law. Maududi was against any kind of Islamic affiliation to secular or nationalist projects that the other organisations were advocating for. The second and the third can be clubbed as the different factional voices of the ulema, though relatively moderate Jamiat, was the prominent voice and Jamaat was the fringe element (Hasan 1988). The role of the first two in the passing of the Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act, 1937 and the Dissolution of Muslim Marriage Act (DMMA), 1939 would be discussed to showcase how customs were overridden and identity consolidated.

It should be noted that it was the initiative of ulema that the changes in the Muslim family law were pushed in the central legislature. As already noted, the primary concern of the Muslim League was to protect the interest of its supporters, comprising the middle class and the landlords. The Government and the Muslim League were able to prevail over the Jamiat in not allowing the agriculture land, which was the majority of land owned at that time, to

come within the purview of the MPL. The technical argument given was that agricultural land was a provincial subject and hence, the central legislature cannot form a law over it. As understood by the scholars, DMMA was enacted to prevent Muslim women from apostasy rather than allowing women easier ways to get out of Muslim marriage (Nair 1996, p.194-195). Hence, the measures that were introduced with the “said objectives” of emancipation of Muslim women were seen as rather symbolic.

The intention of ulema understood for bringing about the twin legislations was to allow for a purer way of life for Muslims in India. In this way, it wanted it to establish itself as the sole interpreter of sharia in India. The primary intention of the Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act, 1937 can be understood from the name itself. Tahir Mahmood (cited in Nair 1996, p.192) explains that it was done only to signify that the MPL and sharia were one and the same thing, and hence can be used interchangeably. The ulema were successful in overriding the customs of various communities in the period of 1930s. Janaki Nair (1996, p.191) is of the opinion that not only did the legislations override the rights women had under customs, but also failed to make commensurate changes that would leave them equal with Muslim men. However, the ulema had to give up the demand of only Muslim judges having the right to dissolve a Muslim marriage under DMMA.

Archana Parashar (1992, p.154-158) is of the opinion that despite compromising on some of the aspects of the MPL, the ulema were successful in legitimising their quest for power using Islam. They had established themselves as cultural leaders in the realm of religious law. It must be noted that despite agreeing with INC on the aspect of composite culture and cause of nationalism, Jamiat’s quest for political power within the Muslim community remained the priority. The question of Muslim women rights—though projected as the primary concern—often came second.

Secularism and National Unity Discourse

The realm of personal laws is not delinked from the whole debate of nationalism and national integrity that was the core concern of the nationalist leaders at the time of independence. This section would attempt to realise where minority rights and personal laws stood in the whole debate on national unity and secularism.

The debate at the beginning of the 1940’s on the “Pakistan question” has now been looked at by scholars as more of a means by Muslim League to obtain concessions within the Constitutional framework in an undivided India. Other scholarly opinion has felt that the Partition greatly reduced the bargaining power of the Muslim minority. According to them, Indian Muslims were in a weaker position to bargain or else charges of separatism would be levelled

against them. Another reason given was that once the partition was inevitable, there was no reason to give in to the demands of the religious minorities (Bajpai 2011).

But Rochana Bajpai (2011) believes that the spectre of partition would not be enough to explain the stance taken by the INC post-partition. Longer-term ideological forces were at play that could only be understood by the normative vocabulary used. The vocabulary of secularism, national unity, social justice, national unity and development were the ones used to legitimise the cutting back of many rights that the minorities enjoyed before independence. Bajpai (2011) has shown in her study that for even dominant concepts of secularism and national unity there were different conceptions at play. Those on the same side of the debate might be disagreeing on why it was exactly so. It should be noted here that minority rights were regarded as a threat to political integrity. It was felt that common nation-hood feeling might not appear if there are group rights available and consequently would be inconsistent for a modern nation-state. While all the political safeguards were abolished with respect to minority rights, the cultural safeguards found a place in the Constitution (Fazal 2015). It depicts the limited multiculturalist position adopted in the Constitution.

The position accorded to religious personal laws best depicted the position of limited multiculturalism and attenuated cultural rights (Bajpai 2011). It was also affected by the ideas of secularism. While the nationalist opinion felt that individuals would be regarded as the primary subjects of justice and rights. For them, individual rights meant complete equality among individuals. The Muslim League version of secularism put group rights over individual rights. For them, secularism meant freedom of religion. A compromise was struck when it came to religious personal laws. The previous protection guarantees provided to religious personal laws by the INC in the Nehru Report of 1928 and the Congress Scheme for a Communal Settlement at the Second Round Table Conference of October 1931 were withdrawn. The presence of the idea of UCC under Article 44, despite being non-justiciable, meant that personal laws no longer enjoyed immunity and were subject to Government intervention.

In the whole discussion, we find that the concern for gender justice had been lost during the independence era. First, secularism and national unity dominated the discussions so heavily that the voice of gender justice was suppressed. Vasudha Dhagamwar (1989) expresses her disappointment that the whole discourse on UCC was dominated by concerns for national integration and political stability. She points out that reform of religious personal laws sees the concern of women as secondary. Second, it can also be the case that reforms in Muslim family law had just come about in the past 10

years before independence. The reforms were brought under the agenda of providing gender rights to women under the Islamic law. So, the call for gender equality could not legitimise changes in MPL, despite the reforms only being symbolic and several practices such as polygamy were in existence. The lack of gender justice in Hindu family code was more a subject of concern during that time.

Test on the Anvil of the Constitution

The priority given to individual rights over freedom of religion is undeniable in the Constitution. Exercise of the right to freedom of religion is subject to public order, morality and health. To leave no doubts in the mind of interpreters of the Constitution, exercise of the right to freedom of religion is subject to all Fundamental Rights enumerated in the Indian Constitution, including the right to equality. It is surprising that the state, the fundamentalists, and some reformers totally ignore this aspect in the Constitution. Another aspect that is present in Article 25 itself is that the state can legislate on issues of social welfare and reform even if it infringes on the right to freedom of religion. Kirti Singh (1994) while analysing the Constitutional provisions expresses surprise that such clear provisions inscribed in the Constitution are ignored.

Another false claim is made that all the cultural practices of minorities have been accorded protection under the Indian Constitution. It should be made clear that the paper is not talking about the protections provided under Article 29 of the Indian constitution. AB Shah (cited in Singh 1994, p.96) makes it clear that “at no place does the Constitution suggest that a minority group can override the fundamental rights even of its own members in the name of religion or cultural freedom”. The claim that Muslim family law is immutable because of the Constitutional guarantee is quashed here. Equally quashed is the claim of the state which justifies its policy of non-interference in MPL based on the Constitution and the claim that it cannot disregard the demands of the Muslim community. The responsibility of the state is first and foremost to protect the Fundamental Rights of the women of the community. This very basic argument would be enough to provide rights to women of all communities and keep them away from oppressive personal laws. But the debate has spilled into other realms with respect to the Constitution itself.

The judiciary has had an influential role to play in the discussion on personal laws and its relation with individual fundamental rights. The record of Indian judiciary has been questionable in the realm of religion and law (Sen 2012). Multiple points of debate have stemmed from the interpretations, judgments and observations of the Indian judiciary itself, that would be discussed hereon.

First, it was a Bombay High Court judgement in the Narasu Appa Mali case (State of Bombay v. Narasu Appa Mali AIR 1952 Bom 84), that removed personal laws from the Constitutional test of Fundamental Rights. According to the High Court, religious personal laws were not laws in force as defined in Article 13 of the Constitution. Hence, they were not subject to the test of Fundamental Rights. The court observed that the presence of Article 44 in Directive Principle of State Policy wanted to provide time for the Muslims to adopt the idea of UCC.

Saptarshi Mandal (2016) has expressed surprise that the shadow of the Narasu Appa Mali judgement still looms large. It has acquired the status of a strong precedent when it comes to cases dealing with personal laws. Despite even giving some progressive judgments on personal laws, the Court did not reverse the precedent set in 1952. It was only in *C. Masilamani Mudaliar v. Idol of Sri Swaminathaswami Thirukoil* [(1996) 8 SCC 525] case in 1997 that held, “The personal laws conferring inferior status on women is anathema to equality. Personal laws are derived not from the Constitution but from the religious scriptures. The laws thus derived must be consistent with the Constitution lest they become void under Article 13 if they violate fundamental rights.” But again, in future, the Narasu Appa Mali judgement was upheld and given precedent. Personal laws have been elevated to the status of Fundamental Rights by the courts in gross violation of the Fundamental Rights of women within the minority Muslim community. The All India Muslim Personal Law Board has brought up the precedent to deny the Fundamental Rights of women (Mandal 2016).

Second, it was another judicial innovation of designating some religious practices as essential practices for the religion that has hurt the individual rights of women. These essential practices have been provided protection under the pretext of freedom of religion provided under the Indian Constitution (Bhagwati 2005). It was in the *Commissioner, Hindu Religious Endowments, Madras v. Sirur Mutt* case (1954 AIR 282) that the principle of essentiality was established. Some practices of a religion on account of being essential came to be protected under the freedom of religion guaranteed to religious denominations and individuals. It is to be noted that the cases that have come up to establish essential practices as a precedent have not been related to personal laws as such. But it has also actively been used as a tool to justify the discriminatory practices against women in Islam. It was one of the points on which the court had to decide the matter of triple talaq [*Shayara Bano v. Union of India* (2017) SCC OnLine SC 963] (Kokal 2020). In every future discussion on reforms, the argument of essential practice is bound to be raised.

Thirdly, the observations of courts on the need of UCC in various cases pertaining to MPL has created controversy and added communal hue to the whole issue of reforms in the Muslim family law. The Shah Bano judgement (Mohd. Ahmed Khan v. Shah Bano Begum and Ors. 1985 AIR 945) and the Sarla Mudgal judgement (Sarla Mudgal and Ors. v. Union of India (UOI) and Ors. 1995 AIR 1531) case have come to limelight because of the push the judges have given for UCC in both the cases. There have been progressive judgments of the Supreme Court before the Shah Bano case on maintenance that went without controversy because the court did not allude to UCC.

It would be interesting to note that the law Muslim Women (Protection of Rights on Divorce) Act, 1986 that overturned Shah Bano judgement has been interpreted to benefit Muslim women despite strong criticism because of the clause of fair and reasonable settlement (Agnes, 1996). Also, despite the overturning in 1986, the Court has found ways to uphold the entitlement of maintenance of woman under Section 125 of CrPC without questioning the validity of Muslim Women (Protection of Rights on Divorce) Act, 1986. Innovative judicial pronouncements have found ways around the hotly contested debate to provide rights to Muslim women.

It can be safely said from the discussion that if basic Constitutional principles had been followed, the road to amelioration of the condition of minority women would have been easier. But what the judiciary has done is that because of its meek and insensitive stance, it has made the road to reforms more difficult, allowing the subject to be politicised.

Political Expediency

An important focus has to be cast on the political considerations that have influenced the decision-making within the Muslim community. Before independence, the moderate fundamentalist stance of Jamiat who were at the forefront of the enactment of the Muslim Personal Law (Shariat) Application Act, 1937 are said to have the maximum influence within the Muslim community and seen as the spokesperson for the Muslims (Nair 1996, p. 192). They legitimised themselves by supporting the national movement. Then there was the more radical Jamaat that despite moving much of its operation to Pakistan, kept a strong influence in India too. The influence of modern Muslims such as Maulana Abdul Kalam Azad was less within the community (Madan 2009, p.172-175).

Post-independence the influence of Islamic fundamentalism continued in Indian politics. A loose confederation of leaders from Jamiat (backed by Congress), Jamaat, and former Muslim League came together to form the Muslim Majlis-i Mushawarat (Mushawarat) in 1964. Its formation came in the background of escalation of communal riots in India in the 1960's. Its

motive was to articulate Muslim grievances and seek to get rid of them through electoral and political process. From the beginning, the protection of the MPL was on the top of the agenda of Mushawarat (Hasan 1988). The role of the fundamentalist has been paradoxical to say the least. While they have been able to grow their support base harping on the failures of Congress, they are still seen as being pro-Congress when it comes to fighting the Hindu Right.

Mushirul Hasan (1988) has also shown how despite differing opinions on many aspects, the conservative groups have aligned to oppose the UCC. The Jamaat has taken the most hard-line position among the various bodies. It has opposed even the abolishing of polygamy as it sees the first step towards wiping the identity of Muslims (Hasan 1988). The Jamiat has agreed with the views and has added that the presence of personal laws is necessary to keep the composite nationalism of India alive. At the 1974 session, the Jamiat announced that personal laws are a guarantee of preservation of self-identity of an Indian Muslim. It is only after the 1974 Convention that the All India Muslim Personal Law Board (hereafter, AIMPLB) was formed as a watchdog body, as an attempt to actively resist any changes in sharia (Shakir 1979; Hasan 1988). The AIMPLB would go on to be recognised as an important stakeholder and would be taken up as the principal voice of the Muslim community in all future discussions on the MPL.

It is to be noted here that the voice of other stakeholders within the community has remained at the periphery. These include women's organisations who have gained some voice only in the past two decades. Organisations like the India Secular Society and Muslim Satyashodak Mandal, who have worked for the promotion of rationality and scientific temperament within the community, and the suppression of differences among Muslims based on caste, have also failed to exert influence. Afroz Alam (2020), in his study, points out that narratives of conservation of regressive laws and practices are used as symbols to obstruct the Pasmada concerns. The same holds true for women within the minority community. "The construction of these identities involves the elevation of women as symbols and repositories of community/group/national identity" (Chhachhi 1994, p.75). Women become the worst sufferers as they are burdened with carrying the identity of the community that comes with keeping up the tradition of regressive practices in the community.

The Indian state is to be equally held responsible for the continuation of the regressive practices. Amrita Chhachhi (1994, p.83) accuses the Governments of "succumbing to and playing off the demands of articulate members of one community against another on grounds of political expediency". While some like Flavia Agnes (2011, p.156-157) feel that someone like Nehru was better at maintaining equidistance from all the religions, Indira Gandhi and Rajiv

Gandhi have failed miserably at that by getting involved in communal factionalism. The opening of the gates of the Babri Masjid for prayer by Hindus is seen as a payoff for reversing the Shah Bano verdict of the Supreme Court (Agnes 2011, p.157), thus soothing the feelings of fundamentalists from both the communities and legitimising their political goals.

While the use of religion for politics by the so-called secular parties in Congress and Janata party has been brought out prominently by the scholars, the role of the Muslim leaders and legislators in relation to these parties is intriguing. Mushirul Hasan (1988) is of the view that Muslim legislators do not put the voice of Muslim as vociferously as they could because they would not like to embarrass their party and hence remain eligible for future elections. Asghar Ali Engineer (1991) differs in the analysis of the Muslim legislators fighting for national level parties. Just as the Janata Party had radical elements like Syed Shahabuddin, Congress, too, has radical Muslim leaders whom they relied on for votes during the time of elections. Another crucial aspect to be noted about these secular parties was that often those outside the Government within the ruling party were seen as progressive, but the Government policies catered to conservative interests.

Also, a crucial aspect to be noted here is that the demand to preserve the MPL featured along with other demands of the Muslim leaders during the elections. These other issues were the communal riots that gathered pace since the 1960s, the issue of Babri Masjid and other related issues. Usually, all these issues were brought up together (Engineer 1990), allowing for an easier polarisation on communal lines. It fulfilled the short-term political interests of the Muslim leaders, benefiting the likes of Itehadul Muslimeen in Hyderabad and Muslim League in Kerala.

The lack of reforms in MPL due to its politicisation has allowed the Hindu Right to depict it as appeasement of the Muslim minority. Hindu chauvinist politicians have regularly referred to the MPL, according legal privileges to Muslim men. They point out how backward looking and misogynist Muslim leadership is the only one that has been catered to for all these years following independence (Vatuk 2001). Along with it, the practices of polygamy and triple talaq are shown to be obscurantist barbaric customs that are completely immoral for the middle-class morality. The English-educated middle class can place itself on a higher moral ground espousing principles of gender equality, national integration and modernisation (Agnes 2011, p.158). These discourses have successfully muted claims for the equal rights of succession in the MPL and the failure of Hindu family code to achieve that sort of gender equality.

Administrative Convenience and Codification

The general argument in favour of codification of family laws has been that it would provide for administrative convenience, prevent litigation due to any ambiguity and provide smoother resolution for conflicts pertaining to family disputes. Usually, these agendas would be at the top for any state wanting to have an effective system of governance. But the issue of religion and politics has overshadowed the administrative need of codification. Still some significant discussion has taken place that can be addressed here.

Archana Parashar (1992, p.243) is of the opinion that a codified law provides the law uniformity, completeness and clarity. A judge made law is difficult to deal with by all those involved in the process of interpreting and implementing the law. Parashar feels that some codified laws would certainly be more predictable than the religious personal laws are currently. Other feminists disagree and feel that the codification of laws is biased towards more uniformity, hence undemocratic and anti-people. They opine that it provides more power in the hands of the state and pits the women against her community proving to be more divisive.

The argument of uniformity also stems from the fact that criminal laws in the country are already uniform. But Arvind Verma (2001) points to the misuse uniform criminal laws have been subjected to, usually targeting the poor and the marginalised sections of the society. He is of the opinion that uniform family laws would also disadvantage a few communities and would be used to harass the communities. It would be better for communities to regulate their own family laws and not be subject to the corrupt administration that the criminal law is facing.

A codified law can result in reducing the influence of ulema on the MPL (Austin 2000). Hence, the focus should be more in the direction of codifying the law clause by clause to which the Law Commission Consultation Paper on Reform of Family Law (2018) is a good starting point.

Conclusion

The different entry points and themes show that the way the debate on Muslim women rights was framed hampered the interest of Muslim women. It was mainly because the rights of Muslim women were an instrumental cause to some other power-seeking goal. Overall, it worked to dilute the rights of Muslim women. The manipulation of how the debate has continued from political debates to Supreme Court judgments is also interesting to note.

The paper, by highlighting the deviating focus of the debate on the MPL, wants to guide attention to the citizenship rights of Muslim women in India. Personal laws have always come between the women of any community

gaining rights of a citizen of India, away from their ascriptive identity (Newbigin 2011). The paper wants to redirect the attention of all the stakeholders in the process to focus on the rights of Muslim women. In order to prevent the capture of the discourse of rights of Muslim women, a framework of citizenship rights of Muslim women needs to be postulated. It needs to be placed above any group or community rights that usually blinds the policymakers' judgement.

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